

Spectrophotometric determination of heparin using phenosafranine and its application

Sun Wei*, Ding Ya-Qin, Gao Rui-Fang and Jiao Kui

College of Chemistry and Molecular Engineering, Qingdao University of Science and Technology, Qingdao, 266042, People's Republic of China

E-mail : sunwei_1975@public.qd.sd.cn

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Abstract : Based on the binding interaction of heparin with phenosafranine (PSF), a new spectrophotometric method for the determination of heparin, which is a pharmaceutical products, was described in this paper. At pH 1.5 Britton-Robinson (B-R) buffer solution the binding reaction was completed within 10 min at room temperature, resulting in the absorbance decrease at maximum wavelength of PSF at 532 nm. The calibration curve for heparin was constructed in the concentration range of 0.2-6.0 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ with the detection limit as 0.10 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ (3σ) and the molar absorptivity as $\epsilon = 6.65 \times 10^4 \text{ L/mol cm}$.

Keywords : Heparin, phenosafranine, spectrophotometry, binding reaction.

Glycosaminoglycans (GAGs) are important constituents of intracellular granules and extracellular matrices of many mammalian tissues with the linear negatively charged sugar chains. In recent years many biological functions of GAGs such as cell adhesion, cell-to-cell communication *et al.* have been found. Heparin is one important member of the GAGs family and it has many biological functions such as anticoagulant, antithrombotic, antilipemia and anti-atherosclerosis activities¹. Up to now, some methods have been proposed for the determination of heparin including spectrophotometric²⁻⁷, HPLC⁸, light scattering^{9,10} and electrochemical methods^{11,12}. Among them spectrophotometric method is commonly used for its simplicity and cheaper of apparatus. In this paper, phenosafranine, which had been used for the determination of dsDNA with light scattering techniques¹³, is used as a new absorption spectroscopic probe for the determination of heparin.

Experimental

Apparatus : The absorption spectra were recorded on a Cary 50 probe UV-Vis spectrophotometer (Varian, Australia). The absorbance measurements at 532 nm were performed on a model 752 spectrophotometer (Shanghai No. 3 Analytical Instrument Company, China). pH values were measured with a PHS-25 acidimeter (Shanghai Leici Instrument, China).

Heparin (140 IU/mg, Shanghai Chemical Reagent Plant) was used as received without further purification. The 1.0 mg/mL stock solution of heparin (140 IU/mL) was prepared by directly dissolving 0.0500 g of heparin in dou-

bly distilled water from all-quartz still, diluted to 50 mL and stored at 4 °C in the dark. The working solutions were obtained by diluting the stock solution with water. 1.0×10^{-3} mol/L phenosafranine (PSF, Tianjin Damao Chemical Reagent Station) was prepared by dissolving 0.03230 g phenosafranine in water and diluted to 100 mL. 0.2 mol/L Britton-Robinson (B-R) buffer solution was used to control the acidity of the interaction medium, which was prepared by mixing 12.35 g H_3BO_3 , 13.55 mL 85% H_3PO_4 , and 11.80 mL HOAc, diluted to 1000 mL and adjusted to 1.5 by 0.2 mol/L NaOH. All of the other reagents used were of analytical reagent grade without further purification and doubly distilled water was used throughout.

Table 1. Effect of coexisting substance on the determination of 10.0 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ heparin

Coexisting substances	Concentration (mol/L)	Relative error (%)	Coexisting substances	Concentration (mol/L)	Relative error (%)
Ba^{2+}	1.0×10^{-5}	4.94	Citric acid	10.0	1.23
Fe^{3+}	1.0×10^{-5}	-5.44	Glucose	10.0	5.60
Cu^{2+}	1.0×10^{-5}	1.15	L-Arginine	10.0	0.70
Hg^{2+}	1.0×10^{-5}	2.14	L-Leucine	10.0	4.04
Pb^{2+}	1.0×10^{-5}	-5.44	L-Tryptophan	10.0	-0.53
Mg^{2+}	1.0×10^{-5}	0.33	L-Glutamine	10.0	7.56
Co^{3+}	1.0×10^{-5}	0.33	L-Serine	10.0	3.34
$\beta\text{-CD}$	1.0×10^{-5}	1.15	L-Valine	10.0	1.76
CTAB	1.0×10^{-5}	-12.52	L-Cysteine	10.0	3.51
SDS	1.0×10^{-5}	8.90	L-Tyrosine	10.0	-2.22

*CTAB (cetyltrimethyl ammonium bromide), SDS (sodium dodecylsulfate), $\beta\text{-CD}$ (β -cyclodextrin).

Procedure : Into a 10 mL colorimetric tube were orderly placed 0.7 mL of 1.0×10^{-3} mol/L PSF, 0.5 mL of 0.2

Table 2. Determination results of heparin in heparin sodium injection samples

Sample no.	Single determination (IU/mL)					Average (IU/mL)	RSD (%)	Specified (IU/mL)
	1	2	3	4	5			
20040910	6328	6232	6232	6232	6040	6213	1.69	6250
20031003	5944	5944	6528	6232	6232	6176	3.95	6250

Table 3. Recovery results of the determination of heparin

Sample no.	Original (mg/L)	Added (mg/L)	Single determination (mg/L)					Average (mg/L)	Recovery (%)
			1	2	3	4	5		
20040910	0.781	2.0	2.757	2.745	2.854	2.794	2.757	2.781	100.0
20031003	0.781	2.0	2.903	2.684	2.828	2.782	2.754	2.786	100.3

mol/L pH 1.5 B-R buffer and appropriate volume of heparin solution or samples. The mixture was diluted to 10 mL with water and mixed thoroughly. After incubation at 25 °C for 15 min, the absorbance of solution (A) was measured at 532 nm against water. Under the same conditions the absorbance of the blank solution (A_0) without the addition of heparin was recorded and the difference of absorbance ($\Delta A = A_0 - A$) was used to determine heparin.

Results and discussion

Characteristics of absorption spectra :

The absorption spectra of PSF in the absence and presence of different amount of heparin was recorded and shown in Fig. 1. In pH 1.5 B-R buffer solution PSF had an absorption peak at 532 nm (curve 1). After the addition of heparin into PSF solution, the absorbance value at 532 nm decreased greatly (curves 2-5). The more the heparin added, the lower the absorbance. Lower absorbance was related to the concentration of heparin. Therefore, PSF was used as a sensitive absorption spectroscopic probe for heparin.

Fig. 1. The UV-Vis absorption spectra of PSF-heparin reaction system : (1) pH 1.5 B-R buffer + 3.0×10^{-5} mol/L PSF, (2-5) 1 + 80.0, 100.0, 200.0, 400.0 μ g/mL heparin.

Fig. 2. Determination of coordination number of Hep-PSF complex : pH 1.5 B-R buffer + 7.0×10^{-5} mol/L PSF with different amount of heparin.

Optimal of general procedure :

The pH of buffer affected the binding reaction of PSF with heparin. ΔA reached its maximum at pH 1.5, so pH 1.5 was recommended. The effect of buffer on ΔA was also examined. Among buffers of B-R, HOAc-NaOAc and $\text{NH}_3\text{-NH}_4\text{Cl}$, B-R was most suitable to be used to control the acidity of mixed solution. And in a final 10 mL volume, 1.5 mL of the B-R buffer was enough. The final concentration of PSF was examined by varying the concentration of PSF and keeping [heparin] constant (10.0 μ g/mL). The result was shown that ΔA reached its maximum at the PSF concentration of 7.0×10^{-5} mol/L, so 7.0×10^{-5} mol/L PSF was used in the following tests. The binding reaction of heparin with PSF reached its equilibrium at room temperature for 15 min and ΔA remained constant for 2 h. The system is obviously stable for routine determination. The effect of ionic strength on the binding reaction was investigated by addition of different amount of 0.2 mol/L NaCl after heparin was placed. ΔA decreased with the increase of the NaCl concentration, which proved that electrostatic attraction attributed to the binding reaction. The higher the concentration of anion was, the fewer the binding numbers

of heparin with PSF had. Therefore, large amounts of Cl⁻ anion shielded the combination of the cationic dye of PSF with heparin, caused the decrease of value of ΔA. At last, the adding order of PSF, B-R and heparin was examined and the results indicated that the best sequence was B-R, PSF and heparin.

Effect of coexisting substances : Under the optimum conditions, the effect of commonly existing substances including metal ions, amino acids and glucose were tested for interference. The results were summarized in Table 1, most of them didn't interfere with the determination and good selectivity can be achieved in this method. Therefore this method can be applied to the direct determination of heparin samples in heparin-sodium injection solution.

The calibration graph for heparin was constructed under the optimal conditions and a good linear regression equation was got in the heparin concentration range of 0.2 to 6.0 μg/mL with the equation as ΔA = 0.0198 + 0.0703 C (mg/L) (n = 11, γ = 0.999). The relative standard deviation (RSD) for 11 determinations of 0.6 μg/mL of heparin was 3.8%. The detection limit was calculated as 0.10 μg/mL (3σ) and the molar absorptivity was got as ε = 6.65 × 10⁴ L/mol cm.

The proposed method was applied to the determination of the heparin sodium injection samples, which were purchased from Anhui Xinli Pharmaceutical Company of China (sample no. 20040910) and Tianjing Biochemical Pharmaceutical Factory of China (sample no. 20031003) with the specified amount of heparin as 6250 IU/mL. The procedure for sample assay was as follows : a 1.0 mL portion of heparin sodium injection was pipetted into a 1000 mL calibrated flask and was diluted to the mark with water. A 2.0 mL amount of this solution was used in the general procedure. The results of determination and recovery tests were listed in Tables 2 and 3. It can be seen that this new method was practical and reliable. The RSD for the samples was between 1.69% and 3.95%.

Discussion of interaction mechanism and measurement of binding ratio :

Owing to the presence of the O-sulfate, N-sulfate, hydroxyl and carboxyl groups in the sugar chains of heparin, each repetitive disaccharides unit of heparin possesses 3.0~4.0 negative charges, so it is easily interacted with cationic dyes by electrostatic attraction force to form a supramolecular complex, which resulted in the decrease of the free concentration of PSF in the solution, and the decrease

of the absorbance value. The binding ratio of PSF with heparin was calculated by the commonly used molar ratio method.

Keeping the PSF concentration as 7.0 × 10⁻⁵ mol/L and changing the heparin concentration, the relationship between A and C_{Hep} was obtained and plotted in Fig. 2. It can be seen that when the concentration of heparin was over certain value, the absorption value kept stable, which indicated that the interaction reached to its equilibrium. The intersection point was got from the two linear curves with the turning point calculated as 9.0 mg/L heparin. As one mole of heparin is defined as the mass of the repetitive disaccharides unit of heparin (wt. 665). So the stoichiometry of PSF/heparin in the metachromatic complex was calculated as 5 : 1.

Heparin has three O-sulfates, two N-sulfate groups and two carboxyl groups per tetrasaccharide unit. Under the selected pH value of 1.5, Hep is negatively charged and with the positively charged free PSF species can be easily aggregated on Hep to form a supramolecular complex. According to the binding ratio which got above, the three O-sulfates and the two N-sulfate groups may bind the positively charged dye cation firstly, then a possible binding reaction process was shown with the following equation, where R and the R⁺ represents for PSF and the positively charged PSF cation.

Conclusion :

The paper describes a new spectrophotometric method for the determination of heparin using phenosafranin (PSF) as a probe. The interaction of PSF with heparin caused the decrease of the absorbance value of PSF at 532 nm and further used for heparin determination. The method was simple and sensitive. The analytical results of real samples indicated that this method was probably suitable for routine applications.

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